

A MATLAB Code for Bi-Objective Crashworthiness Topology Optimization

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Abstract. This paper aims to present a simple MATLAB code for structural topology optimization under crash case studies using an evolutionary optimization algorithm. Yet, many educational codes are published that aim to introduce new methods, but most of them are concentrated on compliance minimization, a rare industrial problem. It is necessary to connect the optimization algorithm with a commercial finite element solver to experience the industrial applications of topology optimization. For this purpose, a function is introduced for finite element analysis which connects MATLAB with LS-Dyna. Since the crashworthiness objective function is extremely nonlinear, no sensitivity analysis can be performed to use efficient gradient-based methods. Therefore, the real version of ant colony optimization is used as the optimizer with the moving morphable components for parametrization. For the bi-objective case study, the epsilon constraint method is employed to convert the problem into multiple single-objective problems, which are again solved with the ant colony optimization method. Results present the effectiveness of the algorithm to derive the Pareto front. The methodology is described and expanded in the text, which shows the simplicity of the implementation.

Keywords. Topology Optimization; Heuristics; Multiobjective Optimization; MATLAB; Moving Morphable Components.

Statements and Declarations

Competing Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Funding. No funding was received for conducting this study.

Ethics Approval Statement. The authors declare that they accept the ethics and disclosures of this journal presented in the guidelines. The manuscript has not been published elsewhere nor submitted simultaneously for publication elsewhere.

Replication of Results. The MATLAB codes and related LS-Dyna keywords are available in the supplementary materials (https://github.com/pooya-rostami1995/Crashworthiness_TopOpt.git).

Authors Contributions. Pooya Rostami: programming, preparing data and text; Javad Marzbanrad: Supervising the research, text editing, and conceptualisation.

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1- Introduction

Structural topology optimization has significantly developed in many aspects, such as methodology, applications, and manufacturing considerations. However, less progress is dedicated to multidisciplinary and vector topology optimization. There is a considerable gap in this field regarding methodology and engineering aspects. The available articles regarding vector optimization are primarily categorized as the weighted sum method, which has many restrictions in finding non-convex Pareto fronts. Also, some works utilized evolutionary methods and heuristics for this purpose. Still, the designs may not be satisfactory due to the high number of design variables, which is challenging to handle. One of the most critical aspects that make engineering optimization problems challenging is the unavailability of numerical sensitivity information. It might be logical to think that the objective function can be approximated using machine learning regression, and then the surrogate-derived sensitivity can be used instead. Nevertheless, this strategy might not be applied to the present regression techniques, which encounter problems with complex and discontinuous large-scale problems. Therefore, developing non-gradient vector optimization methods with higher efficiency is essential for subsequent works. So new developments can be proposed by experts in artificial intelligence to develop more reliable meta-models and by researchers in evolutionary optimization to propose new heuristics.

As one of the early studies on employing multiobjective optimization in topological optimization of structures, Kim and Kim (2002) used a weighted sum of torsional and distortional stiffness for thin-walled straight beams. They used optimality criteria as the optimizer based on density parameterization in which the eigenvalue of the stiffness matrix is considered for distortional rigidity. The corresponding line graphs presented the fast convergence of the optimization process which is the achievement of a gradient-based optimizer. Another application of gradient-based vector optimization is presented by Luo et al. (2005) for the design of microelectromechanical mechanisms. Again, a weighted sum formulation of flexibility and stiffness coupled with a new filtering scheme was used. The new filtering method helped to resolve the single node hinges which is a critical problem in the design of flexor elastic structures. Since the globally convergent version of the method of moving asymptotes was used, and the Pareto front is convex, the global optimality of the results can be claimed. An initial effective implementation of the genetic algorithm using the density-based grid in two dimensions is introduced in Madeira et al. (2005). It must be noted that an initial single objective optimization was performed to present an initial point to the algorithm to improve computational efficiency. Overall, the papers presented a complex but effective implementation. An improved version of this implementation with a chromosome repair is then proposed by Madeira et al. (2006).

A multiobjective version of evolutionary structural optimization is suggested by considering a weighted sum of natural frequency and the min-max of thermal stress to design thermal protection systems (Kim et al. (2006)). The results presented significant improvements compared with the basic algorithm. The authors used no post-processing and the topological designs are available in a coarse mesh. The multiobjective version of the genetic algorithm is demonstrated to handle complex objectives of wave propagation problems such as isolation of broadband lines, filtering the related signals, and attenuation of harmonic waves (Hussein et al. (2006)). The algorithm was implemented in single dimensional problems and the designs were outstanding. Another effective implementation of the linear weighting of objectives for vector optimization is evident in (de Kruijf et al. (2007)) where the microstructural layout of the material is optimized. They used the method of moving asymptotes provided by analytical sensitivities for this purpose. A perfect distribution of density can be observed in the authors' designs, which is a big advantage in the design for conduction. To minimize the morphing energy and maximize the flexural bending stiffness for the out-of-plane loads, Olympio and Gandhi (2008) proposed a multiobjective procedure for cellular

inner structure with applications in aerospace. It is so significant that hybridization of genetic algorithms and mathematical programming was used for this purpose. The effectiveness of this novel hybridization is proven in benchmark samples before applying it to the case studies.

The chromosome repairing is used again for multiobjective structural optimization, but coupled with creating kinematically stable individuals to sustain a faster convergence rate (Richardson et al. (2012)). Besides, the quality of identified ground structures from the Pareto front is improved compared with other implementations. However, a more efficient and complex procedure to employ a genetic algorithm is available in Cardillo et al. (2013). The use of approximated gradient information in evolutionary multiobjective optimization of ground structures is recognized as beneficial in terms of convergence speed and quality (Pholdee and Bureerat (2012)). Marck et al. (2012) used multiobjective optimization based on solid isotropic material with penalization and a method of moving asymptotes to identify Pareto fronts for average and variance temperature reduction problems in high-conductive materials design. However, comparing the related designs with the most recent works would be important.

Epsilon constraining of the multi-objective optimization is a well-known strategy in the mathematical optimization community as a classic approach. Although this method does not produce a set of non-dominated solutions in a single run, it is proven effective in solving complex and expensive cost functions. The first utilization of the epsilon constraint method with evolutionary algorithms is presented in Ranji Ranjithan et al. (2001), known as the constraint method-based evolutionary algorithm (CMEA). Becerra and Coello (2006) observed that hybridizing a heuristic with this strategy may dominate the Pareto front produced by the second version of the non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA-II). The standard version of the epsilon constraint method is widely used for engineering problems such as home energy management systems (Javadi et al. (2020)), while some modified versions are available, such as Laumanns et al. (2006) who proposed some self-adaptive algorithms. Rahimi et al. (2017) hybridised Bender's decomposition with the standard epsilon constraint strategy to produce efficient Pareto fronts for facility location optimization problems.

There are many recent publications regarding crashworthiness topology optimization mostly using heuristic methods to circumvent the deficit of gradient-based solvers. The most recent and widespread methods are EA-LSM which was first introduced by Bujny et al. (2018), and the modified hybrid cellular automata (Afrousheh et al. (2019)). The algorithm of EA-LSM is then improved for different applications (Bujny et al. (2021), Bujny et al. (2023)) which made it an excellent candidate for industrial applications. The main benefits of this method are having a low number of design variables, no dependency on element numbers, and no need for gradient information. The other advantage of this approach is that there would be no need to simplify the problem same as the recent implementations of the equivalent static load method (Lu et al. (2021)). Huang et al. (2023) reported that EA-LSM can also handle structural topology optimization for periodic structures under crash-loaded cases with high resolution in the identified topologies.

This paper presents MATLAB's evolutionary crashworthiness topology optimization coupled with the LS-Dyna solver. A new function connects the optimization code with the LS-Dyna solver. This function removes the elements that must be deleted from the initial ".key" file, sends it to the solver deck from Windows CMD and receives the results from the solver output. The ant colony optimization, plus the moving morphable components, are coupled to solve the optimization problem. The CMEA version of the code is also available to identify optimal Pareto fronts.

2- Methodology and Implementation

This section describes the concept of epsilon constraining in multi-objective topology optimization for crashworthiness and the corresponding MATLAB codes. First, the problem formulation is described briefly. Next, the connection of MATLAB code with the LS-Dyna solver is explained based on the proposed function. Finally, the pseudo-code for the implemented optimization methodology is reported.

2-1- Multiobjective optimization

In contrast with the single-objectives, the multi-objective problems consist of both design variable spaces and objective spaces as illustrated in Figure 1. The objective space involves the candidate points and a Pareto front, which presents the non-dominated set of solutions. The design variables of all components create a set of design variables vector which must be defined (Figure 1-b).

Fig. 1. Multi-objective topology optimization (a) Objective space (b) Components and design variables space.

The bi-objective intrusion minimization problem is defined as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min \quad D = U_{\max}(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n \\ \min \quad \int_D H(\phi(\mathbf{x})) dV, \\ \text{s.t.} \\ \text{residual}(t) = 0, \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

where U_{\max} is the maximum displacement of the pole impactor; \mathbf{x} is the vector of design variables for all components; residual describes the residual, which must be zero for dynamic equilibrium; $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ is the global level-set function for components; and D stands for the design domain. The term, $\text{residual}(t) = 0$ in Eq. (1) denotes that the residual of the explicit non-linear analysis must be equal to zero, and the problem must be converged for each function evaluation. Also, the Heaviside function ($H(\phi(\mathbf{x}))$) presents a binary mapping in the finite element model according to Eq. (2).

$$H(\phi(\mathbf{x})) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \phi(\mathbf{x}) < 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } \phi(\mathbf{x}) > 0 \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

Using the epsilon constraining technique, the objective space will be divided into multiple single-objective problems as illustrated in Fig. 2. The dashed lines in Fig. 2 represent the epsilon constraint lines. In contrast with the weighting methods, the epsilon constraint can find non-convex regions of the Pareto front. The main disadvantage of this approach is the dependency of the resultant Pareto front on the number of epsilons which can be managed by using adaptive variation schemes (Laumanns et al. (2006)). Besides, both evolutionary (constraint method-based evolutionary algorithm (CMEA)) and mathematical programming techniques can be used for solving multiple constrained single-objective problems. It must be noted that CMEA will not produce a Pareto front for each single run, but it is a suitable method for solving hard multi-objective optimization problems, same as vehicle crashworthiness design.

Fig. 2. Concept of epsilon constraining in multi-objective optimization.

Using the epsilon constraining technique, Eq. (1) can be rewritten as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min \quad D = U_{\max}(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n \\ \text{s.t.} \\ \quad V = \int_D H(\phi(\mathbf{x})) dV \leq \varepsilon_m, m = 1, \dots, M \\ \quad \text{residual}(t) = 0, \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

where ε_m is an individual of ε vector which has M components. To solve this optimization problem. The continuous version of the ant colony optimization (ACOR) method (Socha and Dorigo (2008)) is used since it is observed to be the most suitable algorithm for MMC-based topology optimization among other evolutionary algorithms (Rostami and Marzbanrad (2021)). The concept of CMEA optimization with the ACOR solver is presented in Algorithm 1. Algorithm 1 starts with an empty Pareto front (P). In the second step, the lower and upper bounds for ε are created and the lower bound will be considered as the first epsilon value. Step 4 starts a while loop for epsilon constraining, where the epsilon value increases in each step to derive the corresponding single objective optimization result. The individuals were initialised in the fifth step randomly using Algorithm 2, where x_{\min}, x_{\max} are the maximum and minimum feasible design vectors. For handling the constraint in each function evaluation, the exterior penalty function is used according to Eq. (4).

Algorithm 1. The pseudo-code for CMEA-TopOpt.

```
1:  $P = \phi$ 
2:  $u_b = f_2(\text{acor}(f_1, 2g)), l_b = f_2(\text{acor}(f_1, 2g))$ 
3:  $\varepsilon = l_b$ ;
4: While  $\varepsilon < u_b$  do
5:   Initialize individuals  $pop$ 
6:    $w = \frac{1}{qN\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{l-1}{qN}\right)^2\right)$ 
7:    $p = \frac{w_l}{\sum w_l}$ 
8:   While not stop conditions do
9:     For  $i = 1$  to  $N$  do
10:       $S(i) = pop(i)$ 
11:     end For
12:     For  $l = 1$  to  $N$  do
13:       For  $r = 1$  to  $N$  do
14:         $H = H + |S(l) - S(r)|$ 
15:       end For
16:        $\sigma(l) = \frac{H \zeta}{N-1}$ 
17:     end For
18:     For  $j = 1$  to  $nS$  do
19:       $G_j = \sum_l p_l N(S_l^j, \sigma_l^j)$ 
20:     end For
21:     Combine  $pop, G_j$  then sort and select  $x$ 
22:      $\zeta = \zeta \times 0.99$ 
23:   end While
24:   if  $x$  is nondominated with respect to  $P$  then
25:      $P = P - \{y \in P | x > y\}$ 
26:      $P = P \cup \{x\}$ 
27:   end if
28:    $\varepsilon = \varepsilon + \frac{u_b - l_b}{v}$ 
29: end While
```

Algorithm 2. Population initialization in CMEA-TopOpt.

```
1: For  $j = 1$  to  $N_{individuals}$  do
2:    $pop(i) = \mathbf{x}_{initial} + randn \times (\mathbf{x}_{max} - \mathbf{x}_{min}) / 20$ 
3: end For
```

$$\min D + \mu \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } V \leq \varepsilon_i \\ \frac{V}{\varepsilon_i} - 1 & \text{if } V > \varepsilon_i \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

where μ is the penalty factor. Lines 5 to 19 in Algorithm 1 describe the ant colony optimization internal loops. Acor is an estimation of distribution algorithm and represents the Pheromone distribution in terms of a normal distribution. In this algorithm, there is a predefined interaction between the individuals in the population and the statistical model. In other words, the individuals improve the statistical model for pheromones, which is called modelling, and the statistical model (Gaussian model) is used to create samples in the population.

Fig. 3. Modeling and sampling procedure in CMEA-TopOpt.

To implement this strategy, the solution archive S should be first initialized with the individuals. Next, the weighting multipliers w with the selection pressure q with the archive size of N are created with the corresponding probabilities p . The probability model is updated in line 19 of Algorithm 1 which will be selected with the individuals of the previous step. The new population is now created by sorting the new set and selecting based on the solution archive size. In the outer loop, after checking the domination, the new point is added to the Pareto set. Finally, the epsilon value is increased by an increment in line 24. Also, ζ is a parameter that is damped in each internal loop to control the diversity. This is because an evolutionary algorithm must search the design domain with a higher diversity of individuals to perform a good exploration. The diversity of individuals must be gradually decreased to perform good exploitation in the design domain.

2-2- Implementation in MATLAB

The present code is inspired by the first version of the implementation of the MMC method in MATLAB (Zhang et al. (2016)) and a recent version of ant colony optimization in Yarpiz ((<https://yarpiz.com/53/ypea103-ant-colony-optimization>), Yarpiz, 2015). In the linear static cases, it is straightforward to implement the finite element analysis in MATLAB to increase efficiency.

Fig. 4. Schematic for the MATLAB and finite element solver connection in the optimization process.

However, for the dynamic non-linear cases, it is necessary to get connected to a commercial code for the function evaluations such as ABAQUS, LS-Dyna, or Radioss. Fig. 4 presents the concept of connection for FEM analysis. For this purpose, the input file for analysis is prepared with MATLAB and sent to the LS-Dyna manager for analysis in LS-Dyna. After the convergence of the analysis in LS-Dyna, the output files are produced in text format, consisting of ‘nodout’ files. MATLAB can easily read these files to prepare the cost function for this specific design. Fig. 5 presents the flow chart of MATLAB functions and the main script (W_acor.m in Appendix 1). According to Fig. 5, the main script W_acor.m contains the preparation and the optimization cycle. First, an initialization for the design variables is required, which is performed in Comp_ini.m, which is available in Appendix 2. For cost function evaluation, the function Costfunf2.m is used, which consists of the exterior penalty function according to Eq. (4).

Fig. 5. The connections of MATLAB functions and the main script.

In the function `W_acor.m` (Appendix 1), lines 1 and 2 are created for initializing the script by clearing the command window and workspace and defining NFE (which stands for the number of function evaluations) and optimization loop. Line 3 in this code represents the ϵ vector. In line 4, the function `Comp_ini.m` (Appendix 2) is brought to initialize the design variables for the selected benchmark example. As one of the world’s most challenging problems in structural optimization, crashworthiness design is studied to present the effectiveness of the classical epsilon constraint strategy. For this purpose, a benchmark problem was first considered by Bujny et al. (2018). The finite element domain, for example, is illustrated in Fig. 6-a where a rigid pole is contacting the rectangular domain. This benchmark is the simplified version of an automobile side crash (Fig. 6-b). The setting parameters for this example are available in Table 1. A ‘nodout’ point is selected at the tip of the pole impactor in the LS-Dyna keyword.

Fig. 6. Crashworthiness benchmark test (a) Two-dimensional intrusion minimization for the solid beam (b) Equivalent real work simulation for pole impact test (<https://www.nhtsa.gov/crash-simulation-vehicle-models>).

Table 1. Settings for the crashworthiness benchmark problem.

Property	No.	Parameter	Value	Unit
Solver	1	Version	LS-Dyna SMP d R11.0.0	-
	2	Time integration	Explicit dynamic	-
	3	Termination time	10	ms
Contact	1	Static coefficient of friction	0.2	-
	2	Dynamic coefficient of friction	0.2	-
	3	Contact for impactor and beam	Surface to surface	-
	4	Internal contact for beam	Single surface	-
	5	Contact model	Penalty	-
Element	1	Mesh resolution for beam	80×20	-
	2	Hourglass control	Flanagan-Belytschko	-
	3	Element form	Fully integrated quadratic 8-node element with nodal rotation	-
Beam	1	Density	2.7×10^3	$\frac{kg}{m^3}$
	2	Poisson’s ratio	0.33	-
	3	Yield strength	241	MPa
	4	Young modulus	7×10^4	MPa
	5	Tangential modulus	70	MPa
	6	Length in x-direction	800	mm
	7	Length in y-direction	200	mm
Pole	1	Material model	Rigid	-
	2	Velocity	20	m/s
	3	Diameter	139.154	mm
	4	Mass	11.815	kg
Optimizer	1	Number of individuals	60	-
	2	Convergence criteria	10000 function evaluations	-
	3	Number of design variables	40	-
	4	Solver	Ant Colony Optimization Real (ACOR)	-
Hardware	1	CPU	Intel Core i7 12700k	-

The related LS-Dyna keyword for this problem is entitled 00run2.key (available in the supplementary materials) which is included in the supplementary materials. This is the basic model for optimization and the function evaluations for the optimization are performed by changing the elements matrix of this input file. The function Comp_ini.m presents the symmetry of design variables for initialization. Fig. 7 illustrates the component plot for the design domain. According to this figure, the components are considered to be symmetric with the illustrated dashed line. Therefore, there would be eight components with 40 design variables.

Fig. 7. Initial layout for components (a) Component plot (b) Corresponding finite element model.

The vector of design variables for this simple component is described based on Eq. (5).

$$\mathbf{d}_i = \{x_0, y_0, L, t, \theta\}, \quad (5)$$

where x_0, y_0 are the coordinates of the center of the component, θ stands for the rotation of the middle axis of the component and the horizontal line, and L, t are the length and thickness. The related level-set function for such components can be described according to Eq. (6) with $p = 6$ as a constant which is implemented in tPhi.m.

$$\phi_i(x, y) = \left(\frac{x'}{L_i/2} \right)^p + \left(\frac{y'}{t_i/2} \right)^p - 1, \quad (6)$$

where:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} x' \\ y' \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_i & \sin \theta_i \\ -\sin \theta_i & \cos \theta_i \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} x - x_{0i} \\ y - y_{0i} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

The level-set function is also mapped in the finite element model using the Heaviside function according to Eq. (2), which is available in Heaviside2.m (Appendix 5). The Heaviside function is removing some elements in the FEM model due to the binary behavior. To implement this element removal procedure in LS-Dyna, one can observe that this would be possible by removing the corresponding element numbers (and related lines) in the '*ELEMENT_SOLID (ten nodes format)' header in 00run2.key file. Therefore, the lines before and after this header must be kept unchanged which is done in lines 5 to 10 in W_acor.m file. The outer loop for the epsilon constraining starts at line 11. The vector of initial design variables is reinitialized in each outer loop in lines 14-19. The parameters for ACOR are available in lines 20-27, which contain the number of individuals. The design variables and costs are presented as data structures, which

are initialized in lines 30 and 31. The objective function is defined in a function handler in line 21 of the code. The initialization of the individuals according to Algorithm 2 plus the weights and probabilities, is available in lines 36-53. Please note that the individuals are clipped between the upper and lower bounds of design variables. Now, the main inner optimization loop for ACOR starts at line 55 and performs this process according to Algorithm 1. The results are printed in the command window in lines 97 and 98. The optimization results are stored in line 102. Fig. 8 illustrates the flowchart related to the function LS_dyn_Fem.m (Appendix 6) and the described lines in the function W_acor.m.

Fig. 8. Finite element procedure in LS-Dyna performed by MATLAB.

In the flowchart presented in Fig. 8, the user starts the design process by creating the finite element model in LS-Dyna format using a preprocessor such as ANSA or Hypermesh. The level set function is being produced in for each individual via the design vector using the tPhi.m (Appendix 7) function. The Heaviside function maps the level-set function on the finite element grid. In the function, LS_dyn_FEm.m, lines 6-16 present the aforementioned process and find the element that must be deleted. These element numbers are listed in the delete list in lines 17-23. This function reads the input keyword file in lines 24-27. According to Fig. 8, a new LS-Dyna keyword must be created, and the stable lines must be printed in lines 68-71 in LS_dyn_FEm.m. Then, the changing rows must be edited before printing, which is done by clearing the rows that must be deleted, which is available in lines 48-55.

It must be noted that the element indices are added by 1659 in line 48 because the element numbers are not renumbered from 1 to the end in the 00run.key file. One of the most important notes in using this code is that the elements must be renumbered in a way that the lowest left corner takes the first number. In this example, the numbering starts from 1660 (Fig. 9). The elements must be numbered in a way that the numbers in a row grow from left to right. The remaining stable lines are then printed in lines 90-95, and the new LS-Dyna keyword is entitled 00final_run.key. To run this input deck, the system function is used, which runs the LS-Dyna using Windows cmd. Please note that the working directory and the location of the LS-Dyna solver must be edited by the user in the corresponding lines 99-100. The system function in MATLAB is used for running the code according to line 104 in LS_dyn_FEm.m. The system function is located between two disp() functions to prevent the code from ignoring the finishing of the external simulation according to lines 103 and 105. According to Fig. 8, the nodout file must be finally read by MATLAB to derive the maximum intrusion, which is done in lines 106-118 of LS_dyn_FEm.m. The intrusion is finally calculated as the maximum absolute value of all steps (lines 119-129). If the run faces an error or is incomplete, the nodout file will also be incomplete and therefore a big intrusion value will be assigned to such a case to be dominated by other individuals.

Fig. 9. Element numbering format in 00run.key file.

3- Results and Discussions

The identified Pareto front for the considered example is illustrated in Fig. 10. The number of components in the vector of epsilon constraints was restricted to make a faster presentation of the results, and it can be observed that it is approximately convex. The user can increase the number of points to attain a more accurate Pareto front. Fig. 11 illustrates the displacement response for all identified topologies in the Pareto front. It can be conceived that the designs with a volume fraction higher than 0.5 rebounded in less than 2 milliseconds. The design with the volume fraction of 0.2 had the most rebound time, which is approximately 6.5 milliseconds. The resultant structures for these designs are presented in Fig. 12, respectively. However, since the metaheuristic optimization algorithms are non-deterministic, the results might be different in each single run. So, the reader can perform more single runs and average the Pareto front. Besides, to derive the identified topology, the user can load the final design, which is saved in the code, and use the function LS_dyn_FEm.m (Appendix 6) to have the resultant design in the 00final_run.key.

Fig. 10. Pareto front for the intrusion minimization problem.

Fig. 11. Displacement of impactor for considered designs of Pareto front.

Fig. 12. Finite element model for the selected points in Pareto front (a) 0.15 (b) 0.2 (c) 0.3 (d) 0.4 (e) 0.5 (f) 0.6 (g) 0.7 (h) 0.8.

It can be observed from Fig. 12 that the designs with a volume fraction of 0.3 and below have a simple topology similar to a five-bar structure, while the complexity is increased for the fourth design. Fig. 13 illustrates the analysis results for one of the designs, which is the point where epsilon equals 0.5. The figure illustrates this design's stress and principal stress results, number five in the derived Pareto front under the maximum displacement. The convergence plot for this case is also included in Fig. 14, which shows the smooth convergence of the objective and the satisfaction of the constraint value.

Fig. 13. Sample contours for the FEM model (a) y-displacement (b) Maximum principal stress (Rankine).

Fig. 14. Convergence plot for point 5 in the Pareto front.

4- Conclusion

A MATLAB code for intrusion minimisation using moving morphable components is presented in this paper. The code utilizes an indirect connection with the well-known finite element package, LS-Dyna, for function evaluation. The epsilon-constraining strategy is coupled with a non-gradient metaheuristic to derive the Pareto front. The present code has the following advantages:

- It is gradient-free and suitable for crashworthiness design optimisation where the design sensitivities are unavailable
- It can solve real industrial problems due to the connection with a finite element solver, while most of the available educational codes are focused on compliance minimisation in the linear static case
- The code has the capability of finding the non-convex Pareto fronts, which is not possible by the weighted sum method, which is frequently used in the literature
- The implementation is not dependent on a specific case study, and the user can apply any other two-dimensional problem by creating another LS-Dyna keyword.

However, some disadvantages can be improved in the next versions:

- Each single LS-Dyna run is performed on multiple processors, but the optimisation loop is not written in multi-processor format
- The computational cost of the method is higher because of the population-based nature of evolutionary algorithms

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Appendix 1. W_acor.m

```
1  clc; clear; close all
2  global NFE; NFE = 1; Loop=1;
3  volfrac=[0.4,0.5,0.6,0.7,0.8];
4  [variable,N] = comp_ini; % initialization of components
5  %% Creating stable lines .key files
6  S = readlines('00run2.key');
7  data=find(contains(S,'$# n1'));
8  S1=S;S1(data+1:end)=[];
9  data2=find(contains(S,'*NODE'));
10 S2=S;S2(1:data2-1)=[];
11 for bb=1:size(volfrac,2)
12  volfrac=volfrac(bb);
13  %% Parameters for MMC
14  xy00 = variable(:);xval = xy00;
15  xmin = [0 ; 0 ; 0.01 ; 0.01 ; -1.0];
16  xmin = repmat(xmin,N/2,1);
17  xmax = [2 ; 1 ; 0.9 ; 0.07 ; 1.0];
18  xmax = repmat(xmax,N/2,1); %number of constraint
19  Var_num=5; % number of design variables for each component
20  %% ACOR Parameters
21  CostFunction=@(newsol,volfrac,S1,S2,S) Costfun2(newsol,volfrac,S1,S2,S); % Cost Function
22  nVar=Var_num*N/2; % Number of Decision Variables
23  VarSize = [1 N*Var_num/2]; % Unknown Variables Matrix Size
24  nIndividual = 60; % Individualulation Size
25  nSample=50; % Sample Size
26  q=0.5; % Selection pressure parameter
27  zet_param=0.8; % Deviation-Distance Ratio
28  %% Initialization
```

```

29 % Create Empty Individual Structure
30 empty_individual.Vectt=[];
31 empty_individual.Cost=[];
32 % Create Individualulation Matrix
33 Individual= repmat(empty_individual,nIndividual,1);
34 best_res.Vectt = xval';
35 best_res.Cost = CostFunction(best_res.Vectt,volfrac,S1,S2,S);
36 %% Initialize Individuals
37 Vect=[20,20,20,20,20,20]; Vect2=repmat(Vect,1,N/2);
38 for i = 1:nIndividual
39     Individual(i).Vectt = xy00' + ((xmax-xmin)'./Vect2)*randn;
40     % Apply Variable Limits
41     Individual(i).Vectt=max(Individual(i).Vectt,xmin'); % Clipping for lower bound
42     Individual(i).Vectt=min(Individual(i).Vectt,xmax'); % Clipping for upper bound
43     Individual(i).Cost = CostFunction(Individual(i).Vectt,volfrac,S1,S2,S);
44     if Individual(i).Cost < best_res.Cost
45         best_res = Individual(i);
46     end
47 end
48 [~, S_order]=sort([Individual.Cost]); % Sort Individuals
49 Individual=Individual(S_order);
50 % Solution Weights
51 w=1/(sqrt(2*pi)*q*nIndividual)*exp(-0.5*(((1:nIndividual)-1)/(q*nIndividual)).^2);
52 % Selection Probabilities
53 pp=w/sum(w);
54 %% ACOR Main Loop
55 while NFE<10000
56     %% Evaluate
57     [intrusion_max,A1]=LS_dyn_FEm(xy00,S1,S2,S);
58     %% Main Loop
59     % Means
60     s=zeros(nIndividual,nVar);
61     for l=1:nIndividual
62         s(l,:)=Individual(l).Vectt;
63     end
64     % Standard Deviations
65     S_deviation=zeros(nIndividual,nVar);
66     for l=1:nIndividual
67         D=0;
68         for r=1:nIndividual
69             D=D+abs(s(l,:)-s(r,:));
70         end
71         S_deviation(l,:)=zet_param*D/(nIndividual-1);
72     end
73     %% Construction of statistical model
74     newIndividual=repmat(empty_individual,nSample,1);
75     for t=1:nSample
76         newIndividual(t).Vectt=zeros(VarSize);
77         for i=1:nVar
78             rr=rand;
79             C=cumsum(pp);
80             l=find(rr<=C,1,'first');
81             newIndividual(t).Vectt(i)=s(l,i)+S_deviation(l,i)*randn; % Generate Gaussian Random Variable
82         end
83         newIndividual(t).Vectt=max(newIndividual(t).Vectt,xmin'); %Clipping to lower limit
84         newIndividual(t).Vectt=min(newIndividual(t).Vectt,xmax'); % Clipping to upper limit
85         newIndividual(t).Cost=CostFunction(newIndividual(t).Vectt,volfrac,S1,S2,S);
86     end
87     Individual=[Individual
88         newIndividual]; % Merge individuals
89     %% Sort Individuals
90     [~, S_order]=sort([Individual.Cost]);

```

```

91 Individual=Individual(S_order);
92 Individual=Individual(1:Individual); % Delete other individuals
93 %% Update Best Solution Ever Found
94 best_res=Individual(1);
95 xval = best_res.Vectt;
96 xy00 = round(xval*1e4)/1e4;
97 disp([' It.: ' sprintf('%4i\t',Loop) ' Obj.: ' sprintf('%6.3f\t',intrusion_max) ' Vol.: ' ...
98      sprintf('%6.4f\t',A1) 'NFE.: ' sprintf('%4i\t',NFE)]);
99 Loop = Loop+1;
100 zet_param=zet_param*0.99;
101 end
102 f0vala(bb) = intrusion_max;fvala(bb) = A1;nfe(bb)=NFE;xvala(bb).Vectt=xy00;
103 end

```

Appendix 2. Comp_ini.m

```

1 function [variable2,N,vivi]=comp_ini
2 % Component geometry initialization
3 ini_val = [0.38 0.05 0.7];
4 x_int = 0.5;y_int = 0.5;
5 x0=x_int/2:x_int/2; % x-coordinates of the centers of components
6 y0=y_int/2:y_int/2; % y-coordinates of the centers of components
7 xn=length(x0); % number of component groups in x direction
8 yn=length(y0); % number of component groups in y direction
9 x0=kron(x0,ones(1,2*yn));
10 y0= repmat(kron(y0,ones(1,2)),1,xn);
11 N=length(x0); % total number of components in the design domain
12 L= repmat(ini_val(1),1,N); % vector of the half length of each component
13 t1= repmat(ini_val(2),1,N); % vector of the half width of component at point A
14 st= repmat([ini_val(3) -ini_val(3)],1,N/2); % vector of the sine value of the inclined angle of each component
15 variable=[x0;y0;L;t1;st];
16 variable2=variable(:,[1:N/2]);
17 Vi14=[2-x0(1);y0(1);L(1);t1(1);-st(1)];
18 Vi13=[2-x0(2);y0(2);L(2);t1(2);-st(2)];
19 Vi16=[2-x0(3);y0(3);L(3);t1(3);-st(3)];
20 Vi15=[2-x0(4);y0(4);L(4);t1(4);-st(4)];
21 Vi10=[2-x0(5);y0(5);L(5);t1(5);-st(5)];
22 Vi9=[2-x0(6);y0(6);L(6);t1(6);-st(6)];
23 Vi12=[2-x0(7);y0(7);L(7);t1(7);-st(7)];
24 Vi11=[2-x0(8);y0(8);L(8);t1(8);-st(8)];
25 Vi=[Vi9,Vi10,Vi11,Vi12,Vi13,Vi14,Vi15,Vi16];
26 vivi=[variable2,Vi];
27 vivi=vivi(:);
28 end

```

Appendix 3. Costfunf2.m

```

1 function f = Costfunf2(newsol,volfrac,S1,S2,S)
2 [intrusion_max,A1]=LS_dyn_FEm(newsol,S1,S2,S);
3 penalfact = 200000;
4 f = intrusion_max+penalfact*max((A1/volfrac)-1,0);
5 end

```

Appendix 4. form_comp.m

```

1 function [Phi,Phi_max]=form_comp(Var_num,xy00,p,N,x,y,nelx,nely)

```

```

2   ccc=reshape(xy00,5,N/2);x0=ccc(1,:);y0=ccc(2,:);L=ccc(3,:);t1=ccc(4,:);
3   st=ccc(5,:);Vi14=[2-x0(1);y0(1);L(1);t1(1);-st(1)];
4   Vi13=[2-x0(2);y0(2);L(2);t1(2);-st(2)];Vi16=[2-x0(3);y0(3);L(3);t1(3);-st(3)];
5   Vi15=[2-x0(4);y0(4);L(4);t1(4);-st(4)];Vi10=[2-x0(5);y0(5);L(5);t1(5);-st(5)];
6   Vi9=[2-x0(6);y0(6);L(6);t1(6);-st(6)];Vi12=[2-x0(7);y0(7);L(7);t1(7);-st(7)];
7   Vi11=[2-x0(8);y0(8);L(8);t1(8);-st(8)];Vi=[Vi9,Vi10,Vi11,Vi12,Vi13,Vi14,Vi15,Vi16];
8   vivi=[ccc,Vi];vivi=vivi(:);LSgrid.x = x(:);LSgrid.y = y(:); % coordinate of nodes
9   %Forming Phi^s
10  for i = 1:N
11      Phi{i} = tPhi(vivi(Var_num*i-Var_num+1:Var_num*i),LSgrid.x,LSgrid.y,p);
12  end
13  % Union of components
14  tempPhi_max = Phi{1};
15  for i = 2:N
16      tempPhi_max = max(tempPhi_max,Phi{i});
17  end
18  Phi_max = reshape(tempPhi_max,nely+1,nelx+1);
19  end

```

Appendix 5. Heaviside2.m

```

1   function H2=Heaviside2(Phi_max)
2   num1=find(Phi_max>=0);
3   H2(num1)=1;
4   num2=find(Phi_max<0);
5   H2(num2)=0;
6   end

```

Appendix 6. LS_dyn_Fem.m

```

1   function [intrusion_max,A1]=LS_dyn_FEm(newsol,S1,S2,S)
2   global NFE;
3   if isempty(NFE)
4       NFE=1;
5   end
6   %% Finding elements that should be deleted
7   Var_num = 5;nelx = 79;nely = 19;
8   M = [ nely + 1 , nelx + 1 ];EW = 2 / nelx; % length of element
9   EH = 1 / nely; % width of element
10  [ x , y ] = meshgrid( EW * [ 0 : nelx ] , EH * [ 0 : nely ]);
11  [~,N]= comp_ini; % initialization of components
12  p = 6;
13  [~,Phi_max]=form_comp(Var_num,newsol,p,N,x,y,nelx,nely);
14  Rho_x = Heaviside2(Phi_max);
15  Rho_x=flip(Rho_x);A1=sum(sum(Rho_x))/(nelx*nely);
16  Rho_x = reshape(Rho_x,M(1),M(2));
17  %% preparing elements that should be deleted
18  AA = reshape(1:(1+nelx)*(1+nely),(1+nelx),(1+nely));
19  CC = flip(AA');final_matrix = [CC(:,Rho_x(:));
20  secondColumn = final_matrix(:,2);
21  rows_zero = final_matrix(secondColumn==0, :);
22  sh_del_elm = rows_zero(:,1);sh_del_elm=sort( sh_del_elm);
23  %% Reading initial key file information and editing main matrix
24  InpBas='00run2';
25  fid = fopen([InpBas '.key']);
26  Rows = textscan(fid, '%s', 'delimiter', '\n');
27  Rowsl=Rows{1,1};
28  gg=find(contains(S,'$# n1'));

```

```

29 gg2=find(contains(S,'*NODE'));
30 Rows_change=Rowsl(gg+1:gg2-1);
31 fid2 = fopen('text2.txt', 'wt');
32 for i=1:size(Rows_change,1)
33     fprintf( fid2, Rows_change{i});
34     fprintf(fid2,'\n');
35 end
36 ed2=readtable('text2.txt','Delimiter',' ');
37 ed2=table2array(ed2);
38 for i=1:size(Rows_change,1)
39     eddd=~isnan(ed2(i,:));
40     eddf=ed2(i,:);
41     ed3(i+1,:)={eddf(eddd)};
42 end
43 ed3{1,1}=[12,6];
44 for i=1:size(Rows_change,1)/2
45     paiirs{i,2}=ed3{2*i};
46     paiirs{i,1}=ed3{2*i-1};
47 end
48 sh_del_elm_rev=sh_del_elm +1659;
49 for i=1:size(paiirs,1)
50     ABB=paiirs{i,1};
51     if ismember(ABB(1),sh_del_elm_rev)==1
52         paiirs{i,1}=[];
53         paiirs{i,2}=[];
54     end
55 end
56 paiirs_new=paiirs;empty = cellfun('isempty',paiirs_new);
57 paiirs_new(all(empty,2,:)= []);
58 LL1=cell2mat(paiirs_new(:,1));LL2=cell2mat(paiirs_new(:,2));LL1=LL1(2:end,:);
59 for i=1:size(LL1,1)
60     LL3(2*i,1:2)=LL1(i,:);
61 end
62 for i=1:size(LL1,1)+1
63     LL3(2*i-1,1:10)=LL2(i,:);
64 end
65 %% Preparing new input deck for LS-Dyna analysis
66 mm='00final_run.key';fid3 = fopen( mm, 'wt' );
67 % Writing stable section part 1
68 for i=1:size(S1,1)
69     fprintf( fid3, S1(i));
70     fprintf(fid3,'\n');
71 end
72 % write changed middle section
73 for i=1:size(LL3,1)
74     for j=1:10
75         fprintf(fid3,' ');
76         LL4=num2str(LL3(i,j));
77         if numel(LL4)==1
78             fprintf(fid3,' ');
79         end
80         if numel(LL4)==2
81             fprintf(fid3,' ');
82         end
83         if numel(LL4)==3
84             fprintf(fid3,' ');
85         end
86         fprintf(fid3,LL4);
87     end
88     fprintf(fid3,'\n');
89 end
90 % Writing stable section part 2

```

```

91 for j=1:size(S2,1)
92     fprintf( fid3, S2(j));
93     fprintf(fid3,'\n');
94 end
95 fprintf(fid3,'\n');
96 fclose all;
97 %% Running LS_Dyna
98 inputFile='00final_run.key';
99 dynaExe = 'C:\LSDYNA\program\ls-dyna_smp_d_R11_0_winx64_ifort131.exe';
100 folder='C:\Users\Admin\Desktop\ACOR_crash_epsilon';
101 baseExecStr = sprintf('cd /d "%s" & %s I=%s O=d3hsp',...
102     folder, dynaExe, inputFile);
103 disp(1)
104 system(baseExecStr);
105 disp(2)
106 %% Reading the nodout file for intrusion value
107 OutBas='nodout';fid = fileread(OutBas);
108 Rows_res = textscan(fid, '%s', 'delimiter', '\n');
109 Rows_final=Rows_res{1,1};
110 read_row=15:7:size(Rows_final,1);
111 for i=1:size(read_row,2)
112     Row_1=(Rows_final(read_row(i,:),:));
113     rowss{i,1}=str2num(Row_1{1,1});
114 end
115 for i=1:size(read_row,2)
116     LKK=rowss{i,1};
117     disppp(i,1)=LKK(1,2);
118 end
119 %% Calculating intrusion
120 if size(disppp,1)==21
121     intrusion_max=abs(min(disppp));
122 else
123     intrusion_max=1000000000000000000;
124 end
125 if size(disppp,1)==21
126     if min(disppp)==disppp(21,1)
127         intrusion_max=1000000000000000000;
128     end
129 end
130 fclose all;
131 NFE=NFE+1;
132 end

```

Appendix 7. tPhi.m

```

1 function [tmpPhi]=tPhi(xy,LSgridx,LSgridy,p)
2 st = xy(5);ct = sqrt(abs(1-st*st));
3 x1 = ct*(LSgridx - xy(1))+st*(LSgridy - xy(2));
4 y1 = -st*(LSgridx - xy(1))+ct*(LSgridy - xy(2));bb = xy(4);
5 tmpPhi = -((x1).^p/xy(3)^p+(y1).^p./bb.^p-1);
6 end

```